

ASSESSMENT OF TRANSPORT AND OPERATIONAL INDICATORS OF MANNON UYGUR STREET IN TASHKENT

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Abstract. This article describes the transport-operational indicators of the city streets, and the transport-operational indicators include the following:

Roughness of the surface course of the pavement;

Durability of road pavement;

Coefficient of friction with wheels;

The speed of vehicles.

Keywords: speed of movement, transport-operational, composition of movement, density, accumulated density.

In order to ensure traffic safety on highways, evaluation of the state of transport and operation of roads is carried out [1]. Assessment of the transport and operational condition of highways is carried out on the basis of the order of design or research organizations of road organizations, and the engineering and technical staff of road organizations and heads of departments participate in it. When assessing the transport and operational condition of roads, it is necessary to measure the following indicators:

Roughness of the road pavement [3,7,9].

Strength of the pavement. Coefficient of operation of vehicle wheel with surface course;

Speed of vehicles [5]. Below we present the results of determining the speed of vehicles on M.Uyghur street.

Research results: The speed measurement was carried out on the 50 m long road section of Mannon Uyghur Street, opposite the Suzuk Ata Mosque, which is one of the areas with high speed and poor pavement conditions. Speed table and distribution curve graph of motor vehicles on M.Uyghur street.

Table 1

Speed categories (km/h)	Speed repetition	Density %	Collected density (%)
20-25	1	0,8	0,8
26-30	9	7,5	8,3
31-35	14	11,7	20,0
36-40	22	18,3	38,3
41-45	25	20,8	59,2
46-50	18	15,0	74,2
51-55	14	11,7	85,8
56-60	11	9,2	95,0
61-65	6	5,0	100,0

Explanation. When the speed of the flow was studied at a distance of 50 m in front of the Suzuk Ata Mosque on M.Uygur street, it was found that the most repeated speed - the modal speed was observed at a speed of 41-45 km/h.

Figure 1. Traffic speed density graph

Explanation. According to the speed of vehicles in the stream measured in front of Suzuk Ata Mosque, the most repeated speed in the stream was 48 km/h.

Figure 2. Cumulative speed density

Explanation. According to the graph, the ensured speeds at 15%, 50%, 85%, 95% are 30-15 km/h, 40-41 km/h, 50-51 km/h, 55-56 km/h, respectively.

Assessment the level of risk using the "Safety Coefficient" method of M. Uygur street sections.

Determining the level of traffic risks of the road is considered to be the primary basic information in the use of the road, in the correct organizing of traffic, as well as in the development of recommendations for improving traffic safety or in the repair of the road.

One of the ways to evaluate road sections in terms of traffic safety is the safety factor developed by V.F. Babkov.

The safety coefficient is the ratio of the speed of movement on a specific part of the road to the maximum speed entering this part.

Table 2

The limits of safety coefficient	$\leq 0,4$	0,4-0,6	0,6-0,8	$\geq 0,8$
Level of the danger road section	Very dangerous	Dangerous	Less dangerous	Practically safe

The values in the following table were used with the safety coefficient of dangerous sections of the road.

Table 3

№	Km	PK	$V_{КИР}$	PK	$V_{КИС}$	K_X
1	6	2+20	58	2+70	49	0,85
2		2+90	57	3+40	46	0,81
3		6+10	55	6+60	44	0,80
4		7+35	61	7+85	52	0,85

Explanation. The level of danger on this street is practically safe when viewed by the factor of safety method.

Conclusions and recommendations: Developed recommendations on ensuring traffic safety along M. Uygur street.

As a result of the observation-measurement works carried out on M. Uygur street, I determined the level of danger of traffic and operational indicators of the street and street sections and developed the following recommendations.

1. Proper organization of vehicle traffic and restriction of heavy-duty vehicle traffic on M. Uygur Street [6].
2. Timely performance of diagnostic work on M. Uygur street,
3. Timely assessment of traffic and operational indicators of the street [3,7,9].
4. Constantly perform spring, autumn and winter maintenance work.
5. Use of quality materials in repair works [4].
6. Proper organization of traffic at intersections and junctions on M. Uygur street [8]

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